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DERIVOTOGRAPHIC ANALYSIS OF A FIRE-RESISTANT COMPOSITION MADE FROM RECYCLED POLYETHYLENE AND SHRINKAGE DURING PROCESSING

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***Abstract.** This article describes the results of studies on reducing the flammability of secondary polyethylene composites and provides factors that depend on the shrinkage process that occurs during their processing.*

***Keywords:** flammability of secondary polymers, plasticization, thermal stability, viscous-flow state of polymer, derivationogram, deformation of polymers, degree of polymer crystallization.*

Today, various reactive modifiers are used worldwide, including micro- and nanosized mineral modifiers added to polymers based on recycled polyethylene; modification of polymers with dispersed particles; reduction of their flammability; surface modification of mineral dispersed modifiers with reactive substances to improve the complex properties of the resulting compounds; and enhancement of the

colloidal, physical, and mechanical properties of polymers through the addition of high-molecular-weight surfactants.

The production of fire-resistant polymer composite materials (PCMs) by modifying recycled domestic polyethylene with modifiers is also one of the pressing issues of modern science and industry. However, the influence of the type and amount of modifiers on the physicochemical properties of polymer composite materials has not yet been sufficiently studied, and the technology for producing polymer compositions based on them still requires further development. In a number of studies, maleated polyethylene was introduced as a compatibilizer into polyethylene-based compositions, and a technology for its production was developed [1]. In addition, by modifying domestic polypropylene with glass and basalt fibers and a compatibilizer, polymer compositions with high mechanical strength and thermal resistance were obtained, and the fire-protective properties of polymer nanocomposites containing no more than 30 wt.% fillers were determined[2].

Previously published studies also presented conclusions regarding the reduction in flammability of polymer composite materials (PCMs) produced from domestic polyvinyl chloride (PVC) raw materials [3]. During the combustion of PVC materials, toxic gases such as hydrogen chloride and nitric oxide are released. Calcium carbonate is an effective agent for absorbing acidic gases; however, it has only a very limited effect on reducing smoke formation. Therefore, ideal flame retardants should enhance the fire resistance of polymer materials, neutralize acidic gases, and reduce overall smoke generation.

The obtained sample of flame-retardant recycled polyethylene based on the given formulation was subjected to thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). with reduced flammability was prepared according to the following formula (Table 1):

Table 1

No.	Component Name	Formulation, %
1	Recycled polyethylene grade PE I-0525	73.70
2	APP (Ammonium Polyphosphate)	15.00
3	Glass fiber, 17 micron	10.00
4	Ethylene bis stearamide	0.30
5	Antioxidant 1010 (Irganox 1010)	0.250
6	Antioxidant 168	0.250
7	PTFE (Polytetrafluoroethylene)	0.250
8	Silicone oil NT201	0.250

Flammability rating according to UL94 standard:
V-0 class compliance (1.60 mm).

When analyzing the thermogravimetric analysis curve (TGA) (curve 1), it can be observed that the thermogravimetric decomposition mainly occurs within two intensive temperature decomposition ranges, as shown in Figure 1 below. It can be seen that the first-stage decomposition temperature range corresponds to 20.831–292.1610 °C, while the second-stage decomposition temperature range corresponds to 292.16–601.68 °C.

From the figure presented above, it can be concluded that during the second thermal decomposition, an intermediate intensive decomposition process occurs. During this interval, complete mass decomposition takes place, i.e., 98.111% decomposition. The analysis of the thermogravimetric analysis curve and the differential thermal analysis curve is presented in Table 2 below:

Table 2
Results of the differential thermal analysis curve of the secondary polyethylene composition.

No.	Temperature, °C	Weight Loss, mg	Weight Loss, %	Amount of Energy Consumed ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{s}/\text{mg}$)	Time Spent (minutes)
1	100	0.0080	0.3350	13.5330	8
2	200	0.0120	0.5030	17.3600	18
3	300	0.0190	0.7970	15.2880	28
4	400	0.0420	1.7630	9.6150	38
5	500	2.2150	93.00	4.0940	48

Any material expands under the influence of heat, including recycled polymers. Therefore, the volume of a polymer solution is greater than the volume of the same polymer in the solid state.

The reduction in the burning rate of basalt composites compared to the primary polymer is explained by the fact that basalt powder particles within the polymer composition hinder the participation of atmospheric oxygen, which actively contributes to the combustion process. In addition, these particles form a specific fire-protective layer on the surface of the composite, consisting of basalt particles, which reduces the mass of the insulating fire-protective layer and slows down the rate of polymer destruction [4].

Due to the high heat and fire resistance of the obtained composites, they not only make it possible to reduce material consumption by decreasing thickness while maintaining the original physical and mechanical properties of the finished products from which they are processed, but also expand the field of application and operation of such composites.

Conclusion. The article provides detailed data on the process of thermogravimetric and differential thermal analysis of polyethylene compositions, which indicates the high thermal resistance of the obtained material. The research results confirm the effectiveness of adding flame retardants and other components to improve the fire resistance of recycled polyethylene.

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